

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D4.3

Development and application of optimised polygenic risk scores

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1. Executive Summary

For more than a decade large scale genotype data have been generated in large multi-cohort studies from which valuable insights have been obtained in the understanding of the role of common genetic variants on certain traits and diseases in individuals. Genome Wide Association studies (GWAs) have been hugely successful in identifying genomic variants associated with certain traits and diseases. However, these effects pertain to single variants and are not usually significant on their own, hence have to be somehow aggregated across the entire genome in order to decipher the risk associated with all the variants present in an individual pertaining to a given trait/disease. Polygenic risk scores (PRS) are an aggregate of an individual's risk score for a given trait or disease/condition, and are computed from the number of alleles carried by the individual which are associated to the trait in question to be explored. The attributed variants are weighted with a magnitude of effect, which are inferred from a different GWAS having no population overlap with the samples for which the PRS is being computed. The GWAS summary statistics can also be further adjusted according to factors like Linkage Disequilibrium (LD) with p-value threshold adjustment, among others, depending on the data being analysed.

WP4 of the CINECA project aims to create a comprehensive set of pipelines and tools that can facilitate federated analysis of large scale genomic data cohorts. The aim being that these would then require minimal efforts or changes in DevOps to deploy and run in multiple different compute environments. This federated model would not require download of the genetic data, the analyses are brought to the data, rather than the more traditional method of bringing the data to the analysis, thus ensuring privacy and control of the data are retained as required by GDPR.

The PRS use case aims to build a data processing pipeline for the data analysis of genotype data for the computation of polygenic risk scores in a federated manner. The pipeline aims to be modular and portable to facilitate the federated analysis of genotype data at various locations utilising different compute architectures. Portability has become a salient feature in data analysis pipelines to accommodate data governance jurisdictional restrictions and GDPR requirements that are driving the emergence of Trusted Research Environments (TREs). TREs address secured data access and will form the cornerstone for data sharing in the proposed European Health Data space (EHDS). Along with these features, the PRS use case is implemented in a common federated analysis framework as other use cases in WP4, for example using nextflow for the workflow management system and containerization for dependency loading, and has a common demonstrator for all the workflows in the package. We have completed the development and testing of a demonstrator for the PRS use case which can be deployed on different computational architectures and analyse datasets from various sources for PRS computation.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, this deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

The objectives of WP4 are:

- a) To develop a set of tools that would facilitate federated analyses of diverse genetic and genomic datasets.
- b) The tools and approaches developed are backed by clear and practical scientific case studies.
- c) To leverage new genetic datasets with deep phenotyping offers new opportunities for the discovery of new disease associations for common and rare disease.
- d) To create tools to enable local data sources (e.g. cohort experimental data) to m
- e) Map their data to the metadata standards identified in WP3, and locally deployed software.
- f) To create portable analysis pipelines as well as protocols to identify the type of data, type of analysis, and negotiate authorisation.
- g) To constitute the common infrastructure components required to run the federated infrastructure (provided by WP1+2).

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

The PRS workflow (Figure 1) consists of an overall workflow for an automated step by step federated analysis process from getting access to the data and running the analysis. The datasets are identified via queries using Beacon and authorization to access the selected datasets is to be granted from its corresponding authorization process (Elixir AAI).

The pipeline is loaded in the compute environment where the data are present and run by loading the dependency, which is further customizable depending on the compute environment (Singularity, Docker, Conda environments etc.).

The data used for the development of the pipeline was taken from <https://ega-archive.org/studies/EGAS00001002472>¹ (EGAZ00001588936 having the plink files, and EGAD00001006673 having the phenotypes) for testing and validation purposes. The dataset was downloaded from the European Genome-Phenome Archive² (EGA) using Aspera. This contained 84,739,838 variants from 2,504 samples. An xml parser script was developed in order to obtain the phenotype data for the dataset and the height and weight data were obtained for each sample in the data. The genotype files (bed, bim, fam) were processed using Plink³ and PRSice⁴.

¹ <https://ega-archive.org/studies/EGAS00001002472>

² <https://ega-archive.org/>

³ <https://zzz.bwh.harvard.edu/plink/>

⁴ <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article/31/9/1466/200539>

The ONEK1K synthetic dataset was also used for testing the pipeline in alternative locations. This was obtained from Zenodo⁵, and for which a custom set of synthetic phenotypes were created using Phenotype simulator.

Figure 1: Overview of the PRS workflow in a federated framework

Tools used:

The nextflow workflow management system was chosen as the common workflow manager for all the use cases in WP4, as it aligned closely with the GA4GH standards and was flexible enough to accommodate all the workflows used. Nextflow allows portability (different configurations can be set up to run the workflow in multiple different compute environments), modularization and scalable, fast, prototyping. It also provides the ability to have continuous checkpoints in the pipeline, and thus the workflow can be resumed at any point should any steps in the process fail and need to be modified and rerun. For the processing of the data commonly available tools such as Plink, PRSice and R and python scripts were used for the individual steps.

Singularity based containers (Ubuntu amd64 and arm64) were used for the dependency loading, and the development was done on a Slurm based cluster at Helmholtz.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/7619796#.ZEaU3-xBz9F>

3.2 Description of Work

The federated PRS workflow as illustrated in Figure 2 has three modules. The modules encapsulate the pipeline and workflow as shown in Figure 1. Module 1 and Module 2 are run in parallel for the processing of the base data (from which a PRS is initially derived) and target data (the data in which we wish to test the suitability of the generated PRS) respectively, and Module 3 contains the steps for the calculation of the polygenic score. The user provides certain parameters as the input to the workflow which are required for the data preprocessing, filtering and quality control.

PRS workflow

Figure 2: Representation of the overall workflow for the PRS computation showing the modular approach used, an approach consistent with the other WP4 demonstrators.

Module 1:

1. Downloading GWAS file: The base data, analysed data that has the effect sizes present, is obtained in the first step. The user can provide the location of the file which could be a local data set or even one that is downloaded remotely. In addition, the PGSCatalog⁶ util's api can be used in order to access a pre-existing PRS file when the study id and the phenotype is provided by the user. This accesses the

⁶ <https://github.com/PGScatalog>

catalogue⁷ directly providing an alternate source of the base dataset. These options facilitate multiple ways of loading/obtaining the base data for the PRS computation.

2. The effect and non-effect alleles in the summary base data files are identified. This can also be given as the input by the user so as to avoid making incorrect assumptions and computing the effect of the PRS in the wrong direction.
3. The genome build of the GWAS file and the target data is matched to ensure the same genomic scaffold is being used for all variants. Should this not be the case the user is prompted to convert the dataset, employing Liftover, to obtain a consistent genome build across the base and target data.
4. Mismatching SNPs are identified from the base file. These can be resolved by flipping the alleles in the target data or removing them in case they are non resolvable.
5. Duplicated SNPs are identified and removed as redundant information.
6. Ambiguous SNPs which have A/T or G/C alleles are also removed due to the difficulty in resolving any discrepancies caused by mislabelled alleles.

Module 2:

The target data for which the PRS computation is performed is pre-processed and steps for quality control of the data (genotyping rate, Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium (HWE)) are performed.

1. Similar to the base data, the target data's genome build is re-verified, and in case of a difference is highlighted to the user to use Liftover to convert the genome build to match.
2. SNPs in the target data with low genotyping rate are removed, the threshold of which can be provided by the user (default geno value set is 0.01).
3. SNPs in the target data which are out of the Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium are also removed.
4. SNPs in the target data which have a low Minor Allele Frequency (MAF) are also removed accordingly, the MAF value used as a cutoff here can be specified by the user.
5. Samples having a number of missing genotypes are also removed in the target data, which may indicate faults in data generation and thus adversely affect the PRS computation.
6. The user inputs whether or not the target data has been imputed; if not the imputation pipeline is called for imputing the data. This ensures the greatest number of overlapping SNPs between the base and target datasets. Alternatively the user can submit the data for imputation by themselves using methods of their choice and resubmit it to the pipeline.
7. Samples with extreme heterozygosity rates are also removed.
8. Similar to the base data in module 1, the ambiguous and mismatching SNPs are resolved in the target data as well.

⁷ <https://www.pgscatalog.org/>

Module 3:

After QC has been performed on both the base and target data the PRS is computed on the target data, using PRSice and the LDpred⁸.

- 1) The PRSice R script is called in order to compute the PRSice. The default parameters for it are present in the workflow which can be overwritten by the user's input.
- 2) Depending on the phenotype and the PRS to be calculated, PRSice receives the input for a case/control study or a continuous variable for the phenotype.
- 3) PRSice performs the LD clumping and the PRS score computation for each sample in the target data.
- 4) LDpred is an alternative method which performs the PRS computation similar to PRSice and can be chosen by the user (default being PRSice).
- 5) Additional plots for the case control analysis are also generated as the output along with the PRS scores.

The PRS workflow was developed and tested on the EGAZ00001588936 synthetic dataset. In order to test the workflow on the OneK1K dataset, phenotypes were generated on the dataset using the R library Phenotype Simulator. SNPs that were not present across all the samples were removed using plink, and SNP ids were mapped from the Illumina GSA genotyping array to ensure the variant ids of the base file required for the PRS computation were consistent. Phenotype Simulator⁹ facilitates the generation of phenotype based on the genotype data and was utilised to generate phenotypes for testing the PRS workflow. The kinship was computed for the OneK1K dataset, which was used to generate the genetic effects for the genotype data. In addition to this genetic background, effects along with noise effects (random distribution) were modelled. The components corresponding to these were retrieved which were used to generate a single phenotype which was a continuous variable similar to the height data. This was given as input to the PRS workflow in order to generate the PRS for each sample.

In addition the same processes as above were also performed on the CANDIG dataset allowing the PRS workflow to run PRS computation successfully on a different dataset in an alternative compute environment.

The pipeline was further deployed and tested successfully on the CSC compute environment (remote desktop) at Sweden and the Slurm based cluster in Tartu testing its portability (Figure 3). In addition to the clusters, the workflow was also run locally in an Ubuntu VM (arm64), Ubuntu with singularity based containers for dependency loading.

The PRS workflow can be deployed with a Conda environment and also with the modules loaded in the cluster.

⁸ <https://pypi.org/project/LDpred/0.9.09/>

⁹ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/PhenotypeSimulator/index.htm>


```

FID IID In_Regression PRS
HG00096 HG00096 Yes 0.000350890577
HG00097 HG00097 Yes 0.000367072589
HG00099 HG00099 Yes 0.00036143684
HG00100 HG00100 Yes 0.00035572615
HG00101 HG00101 Yes 0.000343272142
HG00102 HG00102 Yes 0.000372544222
HG00103 HG00103 Yes 0.000323478812
HG00105 HG00105 Yes 0.000328960581
HG00106 HG00106 Yes 0.000337211835
HG00107 HG00107 Yes 0.000375174891
HG00108 HG00108 Yes 0.000312786881
HG00109 HG00109 Yes 0.000340842836
HG00110 HG00110 Yes 0.000332457985
HG00111 HG00111 Yes 0.000337580286
HG00112 HG00112 Yes 0.000351164948
HG00113 HG00113 Yes 0.000362586451
HG00114 HG00114 Yes 0.00037775789
HG00115 HG00115 Yes 0.000341353712
HG00116 HG00116 Yes 0.000340780722

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Sample of results of the test data computed by the pipeline

Figure 3: Results from running the PRS pipeline on the test data

3.3 Next steps

With the work reported we have added polygenic risk score calculation to the federated analysis suite developed as in CINECA WP4, showing the flexibility of the federation model to accommodate multiple different workflows utilising the same GA4GH guidelines. In addition, we have demonstrated it is possible to run PRS calculations on multiple different, commonly available, compute environments in a federated manner, thereby allowing PRS analysis on datasets where those data might not ordinarily be accessible for download.

The workflow also builds on the CINECA aim to integrate the work of the data discovery, authentication and authorisation infrastructure and metadata standardisation groups into an end-to-end user workflow that can be deployed on a wide variety of common compute instances. We have also contributed to the understanding of the importance of synthetic data in the development of federated analysis models, and have developed tools to create a synthetic genetic dataset of 500,000 individuals with both discrete and continuous phenotypes that is freely available in the EGA.

The entire workflow has been built using industry standard tools, other modules from WP4 partners and methodologies that can be easily understood and thereby utilised by others, and is freely available to use and build upon.

In terms of next steps and improvements, the workflow could be extended in order to accommodate additional steps (i.e format changes, liftover for appropriate genomic version conversion, etc.) required for preprocessing of the target data for PRS computation on real time datasets. In addition, the workflow will be run on datasets from various population cohorts and phenotypes, apart from the synthetic data, which can be logged in PGS catalogue for future use. Finally, additional architecture related amendments and profiles

have to be added in the workflow so as to run the pipeline on commercial cloud services like AWS, Kubernetes based clusters and Google Cloud.

4. Abbreviations

EGA: European Genome-Phenome Archive

EHDS: European Health Data space

GWAS: Genome Wide Association Studies

HWE: Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium

LD: Linkage Disequilibrium

MAF: Minor Allele Frequency

PRS: Polygenic Risk Scores

QC: Quality Control

SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism

TRE: Trusted Research Environment

5. Delivery and schedule

Due to the serious Cyber attack at the Helmholtz Zentrum development processes were delayed for many weeks, and the deadline was pushed to August for the submission of the deliverable.

6. Adjustments made

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7. Appendices

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